

influenced yield. USG at 75 kg N/ha gave the maximum yield (6.15 t/ha) (see table). During rabi, application method and the interaction of N level and source were significant. At 100 kg N/ha, USG gave the maximum yield (4.05 t/ha), equal to yields with coal tar- and neem cake-coated urea and with USG applied at 75 kg N/ha. Split application of N was best.

In kharif, USG, urea coated with neem cake (20%), and coal tar (1%) at higher N levels produced significantly higher yields than PU. In rabi, USG placement at lower N levels produced yields equal to those with neem cake, coal tar, and USG applied at higher N levels, resulting in 25% N savings. $\mathcal{S}$

Influence of different N sources and levels on rice grain yield, Tamil Nadu, India.

N level (kg/ha) and sources	Yield (t/ha)		
	100% basal	50% basal + 50% split	Mean
<i>TKM9 in kharif</i>			
<i>50 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	5.4	5.5	4.50
Neem cake-blended (20%)	5.5	5.5	5.50
Coal tar-coated (1%)	5.4	5.5	5.45
USG	5.7	5.8	5.75
<i>75 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	5.6	5.8	5.70
Neem cake-blended (20%)	6.0	6.2	6.10
Coal tar-coated (1%)	5.9	6.2	6.05
USG	6.2	6.1	6.15
Mean	5.7	5.8	
<i>IR20 in rabi</i>			
<i>75 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	3.5	3.6	3.55
Neem cake-blended (20%)	3.7	3.7	3.70
Coal tar-coated (1%)	3.5	3.7	3.60
USG	4.0	3.9	3.95
<i>100 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	3.6	4.0	3.80
Neem cake-blended (20%)	3.8	4.0	3.90
Coal tar-coated (1%)	4.0	4.1	4.05
USG	4.0	4.1	4.05
Mean	3.76	3.88	

CD at 5%

N X source
Application method
N X sources X application method

1984 rabi

0.22
0.09
ns

1985 kharif

0.29
ns
ns

Integrated organic and inorganic nitrogen fertilizer in lowland rice

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The effectiveness of urea or urea supergranules (USG) applied alone or in combination with azolla or rice straw was evaluated during 1984 kharif. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was clay loam with a pH of 8.2, 1.10% organic matter, 201 kg available N/ha, 5 kg available P/ha, and 427 kg available K/ha.

Urea and USG were compared at 58 and 87 kg N/ha. Azolla and straw were used to substitute for 29 kg N/ha. P and K were applied basally at 22 kg P/ha and 42 kg K/ha.

Fresh azolla was incorporated 1 d before transplanting. To ensure proper decomposition, straw was chopped and incorporated 15 d before transplanting. Urea was applied 1/3 basal, 1/3 at tillering, and 1/3 at flowering. USG was deep placed 1 wk after transplanting. N level significantly influenced yield (see table). Deep placement of USG was significantly superior to urea at all N levels. Yield was highest with deep placement of USG at 87 kg N/ha. The relatively lower yield with broadcast application of urea was presumably due to losses of N through ammonia volatilization and denitrification. Incorporating azolla with USG was as good as USG alone. Incorporating straw with USG was as

Effect of source and level of N on yield and return on investment. Coimbatore, India.

Source	N (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Return on investment (%)
Control	0	2.8	51
PU	58	3.5	80
USG	58	4.2	106
PU + azolla	29	3.3	66
PU + straw	29	3.3	46
USG + azolla	29	3.5	72
USG + straw	29	3.4	50
PU	87	4.3	113
USG	87	5.2	147
PU + azolla	29	4.2	104
PU + straw	29	4.1	76
USG + azolla	29	5.0	138
USG + straw	29	4.9	108
SEd.		155.8	
CD (P = 0.05)		315.9	

effective as USG alone. The N and P fertilizers might have enhanced response to straw incorporation.

Azolla or straw combined with urea did not increase yield.

The net income and return on investment were highest with deep placement of USG at 87 kg N/ha. Deep placed USG was more profitable than split applied urea at all levels of N. Incorporation of azolla or straw with either urea or USG resulted in lower net income and return on investment than complete application of urea or USG. Azolla and straw involved high cultivation costs. $\mathcal{S}$

Evaluating rate, timing, and method of N application using tracer technique

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To study rate, timing, and method of N application, ammonium sulfate enriched

at 5% atom excess level with N-15 was used as a tracer. The field trial was conducted on clay alluvial soil with pH 8.4, 1.77% organic matter, 1,940 ppm total N, 37.2 ppm inorganic N, 16.8 ppm Olsen's P, 580 ppm ammonium acetate extracted K, EC 1.21 dS/m, and 53% CaCO₃. The experiment was a complete randomized design with four replications. All plots received a blanket application of P and K.

Yield, and conventional and isotopic analyses of plant material indicate that grain and straw yields, as well as total N uptake, increased with rate of N application up to 108 kg/ha (see table). All timing and methods of N application — banding in dry soil, point placement 10 cm deep in soil, topdressing 2/3 at 35 d after transplanting (DT) + 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI) and banding 2/3 in dry soil + 1/3 at PI — gave roughly comparable results. However, point placement was superior. Yields with N broadcast in water before leveling and topdressing 2/3 15 DT and 1/3 at PI were lower.

The % N derived from fertilizer increased as the rate of application increased up to 108 kg N/ha. However, the difference between 72 and 108 kg N/ha was insignificant. Point placement treatment was best, broadcasting N in

Effect of rate, timing, and method of N application on yield and N uptake. Giza, Egypt.

N rate (kg/ha)	Time and method of application	Yield (t/ha)		Total N uptake (kg/ha)	% N derived from fertilizer	Fertilizer N uptake (kg/ha)	Recovery (%)
		Grain	Straw				
—	—	4.7	4.8	68.71	—	—	—
36	Banded in dry soil	6.3	6.8	87.53	7.15	6.26	17.4
72	Banded in dry soil	7.5	9.4	120.69	16.01	19.33	26.9
108	Banded in dry soil	8.7	9.1	128.54	18.19	23.36	21.6
72	Broadcast in water before leveling	6.3	7.9	89.78	7.74	6.94	9.6
72	Point placement 10 cm deep	7.6	9.5	115.17	24.59	28.33	39.4
72	10 DT						
72	2/3 banded in dry soil + 1/3 at PI	6.6	8.2	105.28	14.18	14.93	20.7
72	2/3 topdressed 15 DT + 1/3 at PI	6.0	6.2	87.17	14.82	12.92	17.9
72	2/3 topdressed 35 DT + 1/3 at PI	7.3	7.7	105.66	20.51	21.68	30.1
	LSD 5%	0.9	2.4	21.51	—	5.58	—

water before leveling was least effective.

Amount of fertilizer N taken up by the plant showed similar patterns.

Recovery of fertilizer N ranged from 9.6 to 39.4%. Values for point

placement and topdressing 2/3 at 35 DT and 1/3 at PI were highest, those for the traditional treatment of N broadcast in water before leveling were lowest. *S*

Response of flooded rice to different levels and placement methods of urea and urea supergranule

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The efficiency of urea and urea supergranules (USG) at different N rates and placement methods in flooded lowland transplanted rice was studied during 1982 kharif. Jaya variety 25-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 20-cm spacing in 5 × 4-m plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. The soil (Beni silty clay loam) classified as Aquic Hapludoll had 8.2 pH, 0.76% organic C, 33 kg available P/ha, and 229 kg available K/ha.

Urea was broadcast and incorporated (B&I) at transplanting and topdressed in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. USG was B&I at transplanting, placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills in alternate rows 10 d after transplanting (DT), and B&I at transplanting and topdressed in splits

Influence of N source, level, and placement method on growth, yield components, and yield. Pantnagar (U. P.) India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle	Yield (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)
0 Control	61	157	19.7	1.8	81	2.7	3.4
60 urea B&I, basal	62	167	20.5	2.1	89	3.9	4.5
60 USG B&I, basal	64	186	21.0	2.3	96	3.7	4.6
60 USG deep placed, basal	68	203	21.5	2.5	108	3.9	5.4
60 urea B&I, split	64	181	20.7	2.1	91	3.5	4.0
60 USG B&I, split	66	198	21.2	2.4	102	3.6	4.4
60 USG deep placed, split	67	218	21.7	2.6	113	3.4	4.8
90 urea B&I, basal	68	180	21.6	2.7	116	4.2	5.3
90 USG B&I, basal	71	217	22.5	3.2	135	4.2	5.2
90 USG deep placed, basal	75	229	23.5	3.0	153	4.3	6.3
90 urea B&I, split	70	192	22.0	2.9	125	3.6	4.4
90 USG B&I, split	74	225	23.0	3.4	144	4.1	4.9
90 USG deep placed, split	76	236	24.0	3.8	163	4.1	5.2
120 urea B&I, split	80	250	24.5	4.1	174	4.4	5.1
120 USG deep placed, split	83	265	25.0	4.5	185	4.7	7.4
CD (5%)	3	11	0.3	0.1	5	0.6	0.9

at tillering and panicle initiation. All plots received 40 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 20 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. ZnSO₄ was applied at 2.5 kg/ha.

Based on plant height, USG was superior to urea at all N rates and application methods (see table). Split

placement showed the highest plant height, followed by basal placement and B&I split. Similar results were observed with panicles/m², panicle length, panicle weight, and grain filling. The interaction of N source, rate, and placement method significantly influenced grain and straw yield. *S*